

Registration form (basic details)

1a. Details of applicant

Title: dr.

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1b. Title of research proposal

From Ownership to Access: The Implications of Streaming Digital Content on Consumers, Sellers, and Artists

1c. Scientific summary of research proposal (Max. 300 words)

Online streaming—a business strategy of renting rather than selling a bundle of products—has become a dominant form of distribution in multiple industries, such as music, movies, books, and software. However, academic research remains scarce. The goal of this research program is to investigate how the transition from ownership to streaming impacts demand for, and the supply of, digital content. Using data from the music industry, this proposal advances three parts formulated as interlinked projects.

Projects 1 and 2 investigate the adoption of online streaming on consumed variety and taste. Specifically, project 1 asks whether consumers that adopt a streaming service will start listening to more of the same content than other users (i.e., homogeneous tastes), or rather less of the same content (i.e., more fragmented tastes). For example, recommendation engines may push individual users to new content, but potentially to the same new content across users. In project 2, I explore the implications of adopting online streaming on consumer preference for global versus local content. For example, globally programmed playlists may make consumers more likely to prefer global content; alternatively, as the price of consuming extra variety is virtually zero on streaming services, consumers may search deeper and discover nearby (local) content.

Finally, project 3 investigates how streaming affects the supply of new music. Streaming generates revenues over extended consumption histories, instead of once at the moment of purchase. This may affect artists' production incentives (e.g., decelerating production in some genres), and release schedules (e.g., withholding content for some consumers). The results of the studies will be insightful for consumers, content providers, platforms, and public policy makers. [269 words]

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1d. Keywords (Max. five words)

- Online Streaming
- Information Goods
- Access-based Services
- Music Consumption

1e. Current institution of employment

Tilburg University

1f. Prospective host institution (If known)

Tilburg University

1g. NWO unit (Choose one)

Interdivisional*	Interdivisional	
ALW	Earth and Life Sciences	
CW	Chemical Sciences	
EW	Physical Sciences	
SGW	Social sciences and Humanities	x
N	Physics	
STW	Technical Sciences	
ZonMw	Medical Sciences	

*** Explanation of the interdivisional character of the proposal** (only if you have chosen to submit your application as interdivisional; fifty to one hundred words):

1h. Main field of research

If applicable: also list other fields of research, in order of relevance.

Code	Main field of research
39.90.00	Business Administration
	Other fields of research (if applicable)

Please note that **it is compulsory** to fill the same information also in the ISAAC or Projectnet system on the tab "General Information" (Algemeen) section "Research fields" (Disciplines) before submitting the proposal.

1i. Public summary of your research proposal

Please supply both an English and a Dutch version (max. fifty words each).

English:

Title: From Ownership to Access: The Implications of Streaming Digital Content on Consumers, Sellers, and Artists

Personal details: Dr. H. (Hannes) Datta (m), Tilburg University - Tilburg School of Economics and Management

Summary: Consumers increasingly adopt online streaming services, and thereby give up product ownership in favor of access to content. However, academic research on online streaming is scarce. This project systematically investigates how streaming services for information goods (namely music)—affect consumers, platforms, artists, and public policy makers. [46 words]

Dutch:

Title: Abonnement in Plaats van Eigendom: De Gevolgen van Streaming bij Digitale Producten voor Consumenten, Verkopers, en Artiesten

Personal details: Dr. H. (Hannes) Datta (m), Universiteit van Tilburg - Tilburg School of Economics and Management

Summary: Consumenten geven steeds vaker eigendom op ten gunste van toegang via abonnementen. Echter, momenteel is er slechts weinig onderzoek naar dit fenomeen. De auteur zal onderzoek verrichten naar streaming diensten voor informatiegoederen (namelijk muziek)—en hoe deze consumenten, platforms, artiesten en beleidsmakers gaan beïnvloeden. [44 words]

Research proposal

2a1 and 2a2. Description of the proposed research

(Max. 2,000 words on no more than six pages)

2a1: Overall aim and key objectives

Scientific relevance and challenges

The distribution of digital goods has recently been disrupted by on-demand streaming: instead of owning content such as music or movies, consumers now rent access to large content libraries. For example, the largest online streaming service for music, Spotify, offers consumers access to more than 30 million songs at a monthly subscription fee of €10. In the old model of buying music, €10 would have gotten the consumer merely a single album with 10 songs.

Service providers from many industries embrace the streaming model: recorded music (e.g., Spotify, Apple Music), live concerts and opera (e.g., Het Concertgebouw, Berlin Philharmonic Orchestra), movies (e.g., Netflix, Pathé Thuis), books (e.g., Kindle Unlimited), newspapers and magazines (e.g., New York Times), and games (e.g., Steam). Consumers seemingly benefit more from access-based consumption than from purchasing alone. Interestingly, the Netherlands—the gateway for digital innovation in Europe [1]—is a particular growth market for streaming services. As consumers are increasingly exposed to this form of digital innovation, investigating its societal effects becomes central.

The small but emerging body of research on online streaming so far has focused exclusively on the impact of streaming on producers' profits [2-5]. Missing from the literature is an account of how streaming alters consumption behavior and thereby affects its stakeholders: consumers, content owners, platforms, and public policy makers.

I propose to investigate online streaming using data from the music industry—one out of arguably many relevant industries—for three reasons: First, I have worked with music consumption data in a recent paper, documenting sizeable effects of consumer adoption of streaming on quantity, variety, and discovery of new digital content [6]. This paper currently undergoes 3rd round revision at *Marketing Science*, a top journal in my field. Second, I have a strong network in the industry, opening up unique cooperations with leading organizations in this area (Buma/Stemra). Third, the music industry embraced streaming earlier than other industries, and provides sufficient historical data for my empirical work. Therefore, my findings can impact decision-making in related industries whose transition to online streaming is yet in an earlier stage. In what follows, I will advance three interlinked projects.

Project 1. Does Online Streaming Homogenize or Fragment Tastes?

My recent work on online streaming investigates the impact of adopting a streaming service on variety consumption at the individual level [6]. One of the key findings is that streaming adoption leads to a long-term fragmentation of consumers' listening, because they choose more variety among less popular artists, songs, and genres. In this project, I seek to evaluate consumer effects at the aggregate level. Since revenues in the streaming model are generated by aggregate consumption, determining how consumers re-allocate their listening is of vital importance to right holders, and has important consequence for the structure of the industry.

Economists have mostly investigated supply-driven diversity, i.e., whether the market provides too little or too much variety [7]. In contrast, I contribute to the body of research on demand-driven variety. For example, recommendation systems and curated playlists on streaming services may push individual users to new content, but potentially to the same new content across users, ultimately leading to a homogenization of tastes [8, 9]. On the other hand, because consumption on streaming services is free at the

margin, users may find better match values for their own tastes by searching deeper [6], leading to more fragmentation.

From a public policy perspective, too much fragmentation may be bad news, as it may lead to declining social capital [10]. On the other hand, too little fragmentation may signal a lack of diversity, favoring superstars and damaging independent labels.

Project 2. How Does Online Streaming Affect the Consumption of Local versus Global Content?

A crucial point concerning new technologies is the extent to which its adoption preserves or hurts cultural and linguistic diversity. For example, in fear that globally active streaming providers (e.g., Netflix) may weaken the promotion of local (i.e., European) content, the European Commission has recently imposed a minimum quota on the availability of local content in a service's catalogue [11]. However, mere supply of local content may not automatically translate to consumer demand for local content.

The question at the core of project 2, hence, is to investigate how consumers' adoption of online streaming alters their demand for local versus global content. On the one hand, playlists on streaming services have an ever increasing impact on music discovery and listening [12]. Hence, artists on globally programmed playlists may be more likely to surface in other markets as well (e.g., US artists ranking higher in The Netherlands, only because there are more US than Dutch subscribers on the service). This may increase consumer listening to global content. On the other hand, as the marginal cost of consuming music on streaming services is close to zero, search is cheap and consumers can potentially discover local content easier (e.g., by browsing catalogues by nearby locations or language), leading to an increased consumption of local content.

Project 3. Supply-side Effects of Online Streaming

The effects of online piracy on demand for and supply of information goods have received ample attention in the literature [13-15]. Researchers largely agree that piracy reduces sales, while leaving supply of new products unaffected [16]. In project 3, I assess how online streaming affects the supply of new music. The key difference between the ownership model and streaming is its revenue generation mechanism: under the ownership model, revenues are generated every time a song or album is sold; online streaming, in contrast, generates revenue relative to long-term consumption, with three crucial consequences.

First, because royalties for frequently listened songs will be higher than royalties for rarely listened songs, right owners will earn more from an album's top song, than from average songs. An interesting question, hence, is how streaming affects the composition of product bundles (e.g., albums or playlists). For example, artists may opt for smaller bundles. Second, because royalties are paid relative to current consumption, right holders earn most royalties over the lifetime of a song, instead of directly after its release. This long-term perspective in royalty payouts could affect producers of music, who may shift away from producing hits (high sales and high plays in only one period), to moderately famous songs (average sales and average plays, but over many periods). Third, because online streaming still is in an early stage globally, royalty payouts to right holders are currently much lower than payouts derived from selling music (e.g., \$0.01 per stream, but \$1 per sold track), and hence may not provide sufficient incentive to publish music. As a result, right owners may engage into intertemporal price discrimination, or use revenues from complementary markets such as live concerts and merchandizing to compensate for lower payouts in the short-term.

Using a comprehensive data set (supplied by Buma/Stemra, see details below), I propose to model the evolution of demand and supply in the Dutch music industry. This allows me to shed light on how streaming affects the supply of new music, and assess the development of the creative sector.

Project overview:

Originality and innovative character

- The projects are among the first academic studies to investigate the **effects of online streaming** on demand for, and supply of, information goods.
- Research on the streaming economy is **scarce**, allowing me to become an expert in this nascent field.
- This project is at the **interface of data science and quantitative marketing**; with substantial technological spillovers to students and the academic community.
- This project strives to be **open source**: code will be released for future use (completely for projects 1/2, and within the boundaries of an NDA for project 3).
- Online streaming is **highly debated in society**, and hence answering the research questions serves public interest. Further, the proposed projects are **timely** and my results can still be used to **raise awareness among the general public** about potential pitfalls of streaming.

Methods and techniques

Data

For the first two projects, I make use of longitudinal data from a panel of music listeners—some of which adopt online streaming during the observation period, while others remain active on ownership-based platforms. These data have been collected by myself using web scraping technology from a **music recommendation service**. Part of this data has already been used in recent work which currently undergoes 3rd round revision at *Marketing Science*, a top journal in my field [6]. For the third project, I collaborate with the **Dutch copyright collective Buma/Stemra**, which grants complete access to data on demand- and supply metrics (available at the individual song-writer and artist level; revenue from online and offline sales, concerts, and streams).

Method

Central to projects 1 and 2 is the non-random assignment of consumers into treatment and control groups (i.e., those consumers that adopt a streaming service, and those that do not). To tackle these **selection effects**, I propose to combine a propensity score matching model with a difference-in-difference estimator to assess the changes in consumption among streaming adopters relative to the (non-adopting) control group. Key dependent variables in project 1 will measure the commonality of consumer taste (e.g., how much artists, songs, and genres a user shares with other users). For project 2,

I integrate information on an artist’s country of origin from secondary data; information on the language of specific songs can be coded from available song names using language classifiers. I have gained ample experience in handling selection issues as the lead author on a published article [17] and a working paper in an advanced stage [6]. Further, I am an expert in using application protocol interfaces (APIs) at large scale, some of which provide excellent language classification.

Project 3 will require the **simultaneous estimation** of demand and supply. I already built up expertise in estimating dynamic simultaneous equations in two published papers [17, 18]. I am also interested in structural approaches, and willing to invest in developing the required skills. In my past, I have demonstrated to be a skillful researcher, and mastered new techniques quickly (e.g., addressing heterogeneity using mixing distributions, the analysis of quasi experiments, coding in various statistical packages, and employing make files and Git for reproducible science). Further, the academic environment at my department with its close ties to the econometrics department and associated reading groups will provide an excellent opportunity to further invest into building new skills if required.

2a2: Research plan

Timetable and work plan over the grant period

Project Phase	Year	Project 1			Project 2			Project 3		
		1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Data collection										
Data preparation		■			■	■		■	■	
Analysis										■
First submission			■				■			
Knowledge dissemination			■	■						■

Local, National, and International Collaboration

My host institution provides an excellent fit with the proposed projects. Importantly, I have several collaborations that I can draw from. I work with Bart Bronnenberg (an expert on variety and the simultaneous estimation of demand and supply, cf. project 3), Marnik Dekimpe (an expert in time series analysis), and George Knox (an expert on stochastic models). Also outside of my department, I have several national and international academic contacts. I work with Kusum Ailawadi at Dartmouth, Harald van Heerde at Massey University in New Zealand, and Jan-Benedict Steenkamp at UNC Chapel Hill.

Next to my direct collaborators, my colleagues Els Gijbrecchts and Aurélie Lemmens (with regard to data analysis), and Rik Pieters (with regard to consumer behavior like measurement of variety) can provide valuable input. At the faculty level, the Structural Economics Group, and colleagues Jaap Abbring and Tobias Klein can provide feedback on the demand and supply system in project 3.

Last, I collaborate with leading businesses in my field of research (e.g., meeting top executives of a (confidential) major record label, two online streaming services, and exchanging data with Buma/Stemra).

[1944 words]

2b. Knowledge utilisation

(Max. 750 words on max. two pages)

Potential

The result of my research will be of interest to an interdisciplinary readership of marketing, economics, industrial organization, and the creative industries. Some of these parties are involved in developing this research (e.g., practitioners from the creative industries, and academics from the marketing and econometrics groups at Tilburg). The implications of my work for a number of stakeholders are outlined below.

Academics and Institutions conducting research

The findings from this proposal are important for researchers and institutions conducting research with data collected online (e.g., **scraped data sets from social media**). For example, other disciplines such as management and economics are just starting to realize the potential of this data, and best practices of data processing are not yet established. I plan to **release data** for re-use (projects 1 and 2), and—within the boundaries of an NDA—for project 3. To conduct my research, I need to refine algorithms for text-based matching and apply language classification to large data sets, and code—along with data preparation and estimation code—will be made public in **open source code repositories**. Last, implementations to solving selection problems, which are central to my studies, will have an impact on my field, and could also spill over to related disciplines.

Online Streaming Platforms and Content Owners

Artists and right holders question the benefits of releasing content on streaming services. Independent labels are specifically interested in learning whether streaming homogenizes or fragments tastes, which has important **implications for their business model**. If consumers spread consumption across a wider set of artists, streaming may balance competition in favor of smaller artists and hence benefit independent labels. Streaming platforms, in turn, can use insights from my work to better **understand and personalize consumer behavior** and optimize user experience, e.g., via playlists.

Content-rich industries

Some findings of how online streaming impacts demand and supply will be transferable to other industries dealing with information goods. For example, the supply of new products is crucial for the existence of **content-rich industries** (such as **books** and **magazines**), and is of heightened public interest.

Public Policy Implications

Given the substantial subsidies allocated to the **production of cultural goods** (e.g., books), and the effort of the European Commission to **regulate audiovisual streaming providers** (e.g., Netflix), investigating how streaming changes consumer behavior is central for making **informed policy decisions**. For example, if consumption shifts towards local content, minimum quotas may not be useful for providers of audio services (such as on-demand music streaming, which still is unregulated). Similarly, if consumption becomes more concentrated among top artists, then subsidies for the production and dissemination of independently produced music may be valuable.

Implementation

Knowledge utilization will occur in four stages: First, next to refining my research questions with direct collaborators, I will involve **executives at leading organizations**. I already have good contacts with Buma/Stemra, two streaming services, and a major record label. I will further develop my ideas by presenting in research seminars here and abroad. Based upon my work on online streaming [6], I have already been invited to give international talks (e.g., at the University of Oxford, 2016) and practitioner workshops (Spotify, 2016).

Second, I **present findings to an industry audience**. One of the potential outlets is Eurosonic Noorderslag, a conference with great reach in the creative industries. I have already presented my work there earlier (2015, 2016). Further, members of my department regularly disseminate knowledge via webinars at MSI and AiMark Summits, two excellent international outlets that bring together leading academics with multiple captains of industry, and have agreed to introduce me in those networks.

Third, knowledge dissemination will occur once my papers are published, typically 3-4 years after starting a project. The premier outlet for knowledge dissemination are the academic journals in which I seek to publish. Also important are national and international media outlets contacted by **Tilburg University's team of communication advisors**. For example, my dissertation received substantial media attention in The Netherlands and abroad, and generated new contacts with industry experts. I believe exciting new channels to present findings to consumers are **sketch board videos** posted on social media (e.g., such as the one I produced for my recent publication in *The Journal of Marketing*, available at goo.gl/3qpxgT).

Fourth, long-term knowledge dissemination will occur by developing **teaching material** on the basis of my research. For example, data challenges will train students in the new skills required to work with this kind of data. In 2016, I have won Tilburg University's Teaching of the Year award based upon such teaching material.

[750 words]

2c. Number of words used

Section 2a: 1944 (max. 2,000 words)

Section 2b: 750 (max. 750 words)

2d. Literature references

1. Ministerie van Economische Zaken (2013). Strategisch aanvalsplan The Netherlands: Digital Gateway to Europe. Available from: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/binaries/rijksoverheid/documenten/rapporten/2013/07/02/strategisch-aanvalsplan-the-netherlands-digital-gateway-to-europe/strategisch-aanvalsplan-the-netherlands-digital-gateway-to-europe.pdf> [accessed: 22 December 2015].
2. Aguiar, L. and J. Waldfogel (2015), Streaming Reaches Flood Stage: Does Spotify Stimulate or Depress Music Sales? National Bureau of Economic Research.
3. Wlömert, N. and D. Papies (2016), On-demand Streaming Services and Music Industry Revenues—Insights from Spotify's Market Entry. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*.

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4. Aguiar, L. (2015), Let the Music Play? Free Streaming, Product Discovery, and Digital Music Consumption. *Institute for Prospective Technological Studies Digital Economy Working Paper*, 16.
 5. Thomes, T.P. (2013), An Economic Analysis of Online Streaming Music Services. *Information Economics and Policy*, 25(2), p. 81-91.
 6. Datta, H., G. Knox, and B.J. Bronnenberg (2016), Changing Their Tune: How Consumers' Adoption of Online Streaming Affects Music Consumption and Discovery. Working Paper, under 3rd round revision at Marketing Science.
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 8. Fleder, D. and K. Hosanagar (2009), Blockbuster Culture's Next Rise or Fall: The Impact of Recommender Systems on Sales Diversity. *Management Science*, 55(5), p. 697-712.
 9. Hosanagar, K., et al. (2014), Will the Global Village Fracture Into Tribes? Recommender Systems and Their Effects on Consumer Fragmentation. *Management Science*, 60(4), p. 805-823.
 10. Putnam, R.D., *Bowling Alone: America's Declining Social Capital*, in *Culture and Politics: A Reader*, L. Crothers and C. Lockhart, Editors. 2000, Palgrave Macmillan US: New York. p. 223-234.
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 12. Musically (2016). Spotify Keen To Avoid Homogeneity From Global Playlists. Available from: <http://musically.com/2016/10/28/spotify-keen-avoid-homogeneity-global-playlists/> [accessed: 6 January 2017].
 13. Oberholzer-Gee, F. and K. Strumpf (2007), The Effect of File Sharing on Record Sales: An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Political Economy*, 115(1), p. 1-42.
 14. Liebowitz, S.J. (2008), Testing File-Sharing's Impact by Examining Record Sales in Cities. *Management Science*, 54(4), p. 852-859.
 15. Rob, R. and J. Waldfogel (2006), Piracy on the High C's: Music Downloading, Sales Displacement, and Social Welfare in a Sample of College Students. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 49(1), p. 29-62.
 16. Waldfogel, J. (2012), Music Piracy and Its Effects on Demand, Supply, and Welfare. National Bureau of Economic Research.
 17. Datta, H., B. Foubert, and H.J. Van Heerde (2015), The Challenge of Retaining Customers Acquired with Free Trials. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(2), p. 217-234.
 18. Datta, H., K.L. Ailawadi, and H.J. van Heerde (2016), How Well Does Consumer-Based Brand Equity Align with Sales-Based Brand Equity and Marketing Mix Response? *Journal of Marketing*.

2e. Datamanagement

Responsible data management is part of good research. For the collection/generation of data and the analysis of this data, timely measures need to be taken to ensure the storage and later reuse of the data. This means that prior to the start of the research project researchers must ascertain a) which data could be relevant and b) how these data could be stored so that they are accessible for reuse. After a proposal has been awarded funding, the researcher will draw up a detailed data management plan in which the researcher explains how all relevant data research data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

NWO understands 'data' to be both collected, unprocessed data as well as analysed, generated data. Under this all forms are conceivable; digital and non-digital (for example samples, completed questionnaires, sound recordings, etc.). NWO only requests storage of reusable relevant data.

See the explanatory note as well.

Please answer the following questions:

1. Will data be collected or generated that are suitable for reuse?

Yes.

2. Where will the data be stored during the research?

Next to storing working copies of relevant files on my local computer, I already use the following systems for my research (and will continue doing so for the projects described in this grant proposal):

- I store my raw data on Beehub.nl, a facility by SurfSara providing secure data storage services.
- I complement Beehub.nl with file storage and data base services (e.g., NoSQL) at the EU-based Amazon Cloud (which are not available at the national level).
- All my code is stored at private GitHub repositories. Once a project is finalized, I can make these repositories public.

3. After the project has been completed, how will the data be stored for the long-term and made available for the use by third parties? To whom will the data be accessible?

- Data format
 - I already make use of platform-independent formats (e.g., CSV files), instead of files suitable for only specific software programs (e.g., .RData from R, or .dat from Stata)
- Accessibility
 - Some of the journals I seek to publish in provide their own infrastructure to providing long-term access for the use by third parties, e.g., *Marketing Science*.¹
 - Long-term access can be provided via DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services), an institute of KNAW.

4. Which facilities (ICT, (secure) archive, refrigerators or legal expertise) do you expect will be needed for the storage of data during the research and after the research? Are these available?*

- I will make use of the Dutch eInfrastructure. I have already experience from prior projects on this infrastructure (grants e-infra130055 and e-infra140195).
- Legal Expertise can be provided by the University support, especially concerning the company data used in project 3.

*ICT facilities for data storage are considered to be resources such as data storage capacity, bandwidth for data transport and calculating power for data processing.

¹ Desai, P. S. (2013). Marketing Science Replication and Disclosure Policy. *Marketing Science*, 32(1), 1-3.

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Veni scheme

Cost estimates

3a. Budget

The maximum amount of a Veni grant is € 250,000 to be spent over a period of three years. If the proposed research is of shorter duration, the maximum amount will be reduced accordingly.

	Description			Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
Staff		FTE**	Months				
WP*	Applicant	1fte	36	<i>Salary data has been removed</i>			
NWP*							
Total Staff							
Equipment							
Total Equipment							
Investments							
Total Investments							
Materials							
Total Materials							
Travel	Conferences and stay abroad			3,000	3,000	2,000	8,000
Total Travel							
Other	Hosting workshop on reproducible science			2,500	0	0	2,500
Total Other							
Grand total							

Please note:

- Use one row each for each staff member, type of equipment, type of investment or type of material (e.g., data management costs) one row. Additional rows (as many as you need) should be added underneath the bold print headings, listing all items separately. You should not add headings.
- Years are Project Years. For example: if your intended starting date is 1 October 2017, then Year 1 ranges from 1 October 2017 to 30 September 2018.

* WP = Scientific staff; NWP = Non-scientific staff

** Please list the time you will spend on your Veni, including any FTE percentage that your host institution will pay of your salary for your work on this Veni project. If your host institution pays for (part of) the time you spend on your Veni, please include this information in section 3b.

3b. Co-financing 'in kind'

Co-financer / party	Description	Estimated value in euros
Tilburg University	Contribution towards salary costs	[data removed]

3c. Cofinancing 'in cash'

Co-financer / party	Description	euros
..

3d. Totals

Grand total	_____ (=3a)
Requested budget	250,000 (=3a minus 3b and 3c)

3e. Intended starting date September 1, 2017

3f. Have you applied for any additional grants for this project either from NWO or from any other institution, and/or has the same idea been submitted elsewhere? yes/no (If yes, please provide details)

No.

Curriculum vitae

4a. Personal details

Title(s), initial(s), first name, surname: dr. H. (Hannes) Datta

Gender: male

Date of birth: 4 July 1984

Nationality: German

4b. Master's degree ('doctoraal')

University/College of Higher Education: Maastricht University

Date (dd/mm/yy): 31/8/2010

Main subject: Business Research, M.Sc. (cum laude)

4c. Doctorate

University/College of Higher Education: Maastricht University

Starting date (dd/mm/yy): 01/09/2010

Date of PhD award (dd/mm/yy): 07/02/2014

Supervisor ('Promotor'): prof. Harald J. van Heerde, dr. Bram Foubert, prof. Martin Wetzels

Title of thesis: It's In The Way That You Use It: Usage Behavior, Sales Performance, and Their Interrelationships

4d. Work experience since completing your PhD

Position	Period (date-date)	FTE	Type of position (fixed term/ permanent/ tenure track/ other)	Institution
Assistant Professor	01-09-2013 (PhD obtained in 2014)	1.0	Tenure track	Tilburg University

Months spent since completing your PhD

(Please also include the calculation)

Experience	Number of months
Research activities	60% of 35 months = 21
Education	40% of 35 months = 14
Care or sick leave	0%
Management tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involvement in data science initiative of Tilburg University and TU Eindhoven Planning of new M.Sc. Marketing Analytics program
Other, please specify	

4e. Academic staff supervised

	Give names or numbers	Please indicate with "x" whether your role was/is a formal/informal one and briefly clarify your precise role in the column to the very right.		
PhDs		Formal role	Informal role	Clarification
Ongoing	5		x	Feedback to PhD students at my faculty (e.g., on setting up online data collections, scientific programming, modeling)
Successfully completed	<i>Names</i>			
<i>Subtotal PhDs</i>	<i>Total number</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Number</i>	
Postdocs				
	<i>Names</i>	<i>Specify your role</i>		
<i>Subtotal postdocs</i>	<i>Total number</i>			
Master students				
<i>Subtotal master students</i>	25 (since obtaining my PhD) 30 (during my PhD and as an Assistant Professor) 55 in total	<i>Specify your role</i>		
Other				
<i>Subtotal other</i>	<i>Numbers</i>	<i>Specify your role</i>		

4f. Brief summary of your research over the last five years

(Max. 250 words)

I have developed and applied advanced econometric models in the areas of access-based services (e.g., free trials for digital TV), and digital markets (e.g., adoption of online streaming and online piracy).

Given the substantial investment in new data collection methods and high performance computing on the Dutch national eInfrastructure, my PhD consisted of two projects. In my first essay, I studied the effectiveness of free-trial promotions for customer lifetime value. Using panel data from a digital TV service, I used quasi-experimental methods to demonstrate permanent behavioral differences, making free-trial customers worth less than regular customers, but more responsive to changes in marketing communication and usage rates. This paper has been published in *Journal of Marketing Research*, and was one out of five finalists for the 2016 Best Paper Award. In my second study, I demonstrated that online piracy of music reduces sales, but increases consumer engagement with artists, thereby mitigating piracy's negative sales impact. This paper has been revised recently, and is currently under friendly review by a senior colleague at my department.

After being appointed at Tilburg University, I have expanded into the area of digital media consumption (my work on streaming currently undergoes revision at *Marketing Science*), and gained substantial experience working with large data sets. Apart from my interest in new media, I work on projects in the area of retailing. For example, in recently published work at the *Journal of Marketing*, I assess the relationship between consumer-based and sales-based brand equity.

[245 words]

4g. International activities

University of Tübingen (Germany)

- 1-2 December 2016
- 20-23 May 2013
- 4-8 February 2013

Waikato University, Hamilton (New Zealand)

- 3 January – 16 April 2012

Invited research presentations

- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (19 April 2017; scheduled)
- London Business School (20 March 2017; scheduled)
- Wageningen University (12 December 2016)
- University of Oxford, Saïd Business School (22 September 2016)
- Catholic University of Leuven and Vlerick Business School, Leuven (9 September 2016)
- Amsterdam Business School (9 April 2016)
- 3rd Symposium on Value Creation in a Changing Customer and Media Environment, Cologne University, Germany (9 July 2015)
- Rijksuniversiteit Groningen (24 June 2014)
- Erasmus University, Rotterdam (17 September 2012)
- Tilburg University (5 September 2012)
- Waikato School of Management, Hamilton, New Zealand (7 February 2012)

International conference Presentations

- Marketing Science, Los Angeles (June 2017; scheduled)
- Marketing Science, Shanghai (16-18 June 2016)
- Marketing Dynamics, Hamburg (6-9 July 2016)
- European Marketing Association Conference, Leuven (26-29 May 2015)
- Big Data, Mobile Targeting and Social Media Marketing, LMU Munich (13 March 2015)
- Marketing Dynamics, Stanford University and the University of Chicago, Las Vegas (23 August 2014)
- Marketing Science Conference, Özyeğin University, Istanbul (11-13 July 2013)
- European Marketing Association Conference, Lisbon (22-25 May 2012)
- Marketing Dynamics Conference, Tilburg University (23-25 August 2012)
- Marketing Science Conference, Boston (7-9 June 2012)

International Collaborators

- Kusum L. Ailawadi, Charles Jordan 1911 TU'12 Professor of Marketing, Tuck School of Business, Dartmouth College, USA
- Harald van Heerde, Research Professor of Marketing, Massey University, New Zealand
- Dominik Papies, Professor of Marketing, Tübingen University, Germany
- Jan-Benedict Steenkamp, Knox Massey Distinguished Professor of Marketing and Area Chair of Marketing, UNC Chapel Hill, USA

4h. Other academic activities

Invited conferences

- Invitational Choice Symposium, University of Alberta and University of St. Gallen (14-17 May 2016)
- Eurosonic Noorderslag Conference, Groningen (15 January 2016)
- Paaspop Academy, Schijndel (3 April 2015)
- Eurosonic Noorderslag Conference, Groningen (15 January 2015)

Ad hoc reviewer for:

- Marketing Science
- Journal of Marketing Research
- International Journal of Research in Marketing
- Journal of Interactive Marketing
- European Marketing Academy Conference

Member of

- INFORMS Society for Marketing Science (ISMS)
- European Marketing Academy (EMAC)

Committees:

- Member of the sounding board for the KNAW-committee "Big Data" (4 November 2016)

Organizational tasks-Membership:

As an Assistant Professor at Tilburg University

- Conceptualization of new M.Sc. in Marketing Analytics
- Member of Data Science Initiative (development of new B.Sc. Data Science)
- IT-infrastructure committee of the faculty
- Implementation of Google Online Marketing Challenge for M.Sc. students

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During PhD at Maastricht University

- Scientific programming support
- Website committee

4i. Scholarships, grants and prizes

Please list the research scholarships/grants and a link to the website for which you have successfully applied and/or prizes that you have won and indicate the amount of money involved.

*In case of a consortium grant please specify the amount allocated for your own group or lab.

Scholarship/Grant/ Prize Formal applicant	Amount in euros	*	Year of award
Tilburg School of Economics and Business, towards developing a research agenda on online streaming (data science grant)	€50,000		2016
Finalist for the best paper award in <i>Journal of Marketing Research</i> (one out of only 5 finalists)			2016
Tilburg University's Best Teacher Award (selected by a jury)			2016
MSI Research Proposal Competition (MSI 4-1854)	€3,650 (\$4,000)		2015
Finalist for the European Marketing Academy Best Paper Award based on a Dissertation (honorable mention)	-		2015
National eInfrastructure (e-infra140195)	Computing infrastructure (20,000 core hours, 1TB storage, worth €1,143 ¹)		2014
National eInfrastructure (e-infra130055)	Computing infrastructure (50,000 core hours, 1TB storage, worth €2,938 ²)		2013
47 th AMA-Sheth Doctoral Consortium Fellow, Seattle	-		2012
Maastricht Graduate School Travel Grant	€4,000		2012
EMAC Doctoral Colloquium Fellow (Advanced Track)	-		2011
<i>Subtotal</i>	€61,731		
Scholarship/Grant/Prize Formal co-applicant			
<i>Subtotal</i>			
<i>Total</i>	€61,731		

² Calculated by SurfSara (correspondence with Frank Heere (frank.heere@surfsara.nl) on December 13, 2015).

Output

5a. Output indicators

Please identify the most important output indicators in your field.

Publications: *Journal of Marketing Research*, *Journal of Marketing* and *Marketing Science* are considered top outlets in Marketing.

Co-authorship:

- First authors usually contribute the most, and take a significant lead in data preparation, analysis, and writing the paper.
- Working together with senior co-authors is considered a sign of quality and good practice at the start of one's career. Senior co-authors typically have a mentoring role in projects.
- Single-authored publications at the start of one's career are the exception in the marketing field.

5b. Top publications (Max. five)

Please motivate your selection.

- Hannes Datta, Kusum L. Ailawadi, and Harald J. van Heerde (in press). How Well Does Consumer-Based Brand Equity Align with Sales-Based Brand Equity and Marketing Mix Response? *Journal of Marketing*. Available at: <http://journals.ama.org/doi/abs/10.1509/jm.15.0340>
 - For this project, I have coded a seemingly unrelated regression estimator in R, and optimized its performance using Sparse matrix algebra so that it becomes scalable to a large number of simultaneous equations. My experience in manually coding estimators (rather than resorting to ready-made packages) will be a useful skill when developing complex estimations techniques for project 3 (e.g., the joint demand and supply system).
- Hannes Datta, Bram Foubert and Harald J. Van Heerde (2015). The Challenge of Retaining Customers Acquired with Free Trials. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(2), 217-234. Available at: <http://journals.ama.org/doi/abs/10.1509/jmr.12.0160>
 - This paper is one of the first studies in Marketing to directly model usage/consumption of digital media; I have built up significant expertise on usage data, which is similar to the music consumption data dealt with in projects 1 and 2.
 - This paper employs propensity score matching to address the non-random assignment of users to the treatment group; I have gained substantial knowledge in this area (see also Datta/Knox/Bronnenberg, listed as a working paper below), which is relevant for working on projects 1-2.
 - Further, this project involves estimating dynamic simultaneous equations on the national eInfrastructure using simulated maximum likelihood; my ability to estimate them efficiently using high performance computing will help me to make fast progress on the projects in this proposal.

5c. Output

Please number your items consecutively and also indicate the total number per category. For publications and letters: only mention those that have been published or have been accepted for publication starting with the most recent publication, do **not** list any forthcoming publications. Please mark key publications that are directly relevant to the proposed research with an S (the S stands for significant).

- **Refereed articles [2]**

- Hannes Datta, Kusum L. Ailawadi, and Harald J. van Heerde (in press). How Well Does Consumer-Based Brand Equity Align with Sales-Based Brand Equity and Marketing Mix Response? *Journal of Marketing*. Available at: journals.ama.org/doi/abs/10.1509/jm.15.0340
- Hannes Datta, Bram Foubert and Harald J. Van Heerde (2015). The Challenge of Retaining Customers Acquired with Free Trials. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 52(2), 217-234. Available at: <http://journals.ama.org/doi/abs/10.1509/jmr.12.0160>

- **Selected Work in Progress [3]**

- Datta, Hannes, George Knox, and Bart Bronnenberg. "Changing Their Tune: How Consumers' Adoption of Online Streaming Affects Music Consumption and Discovery" [S].

Currently undergoing 3rd round revision at *Marketing Science*. Available at go.uvt.nl/spotify.
- Datta, Hannes, Bram Foubert and Dominik Papies, "Usage Rates, Facebook Likes, and Online Piracy: Using Big Data to Manage Entertainment Products", undergoing friendly review by senior colleague.
- Datta, Hannes, Marnik G. Dekimpe, Harald J. van Heerde, and Jan-Benedict E.M. Steenkamp, "Marketing Effectiveness for Electronic Goods in Emerging Markets", models estimated; writing phase.

5d. Median impact factors for your own field

For all NWO units, this is only compulsory if you have mentioned impact factors of the journal under question 5c, above.

N/A.

Statements by the applicant

Use of extension clause: yes/no

(if 'yes', give reasons and calculation, plus date of NWO confirmation (e-mail) that extension was granted)

- My thesis manuscript has been approved and I will send the official declaration to NWO.**
(Compulsory only for Veni applicants who have not yet received their doctorates, to be sent by post and as a PDF using the electronic system.)

Ethical aspects

	Not applicable	Not yet applied for	Applied for	Received
Approval from a recognised medical ethics review committee	x			
Approval from an animal experiments committee	x			
Permission for research with the population screening Act	x			

If applicable, send a copy of (one of) the aforementioned documents to NWO before the start of your project, if your application has been granted.

By submitting this form I endorse the code of conduct for laboratory animals and the code of conduct for biosecurity/possibility for dual use of the expected results and will act accordingly if applicable.

- I have completed this form truthfully.
- By submitting this document I declare that I satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the *Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice 2012*¹ (Association of Universities in the Netherlands)
- I have submitted non-referees.²

Name: Hannes Datta

Place: Tilburg

Date: 10 January 2017

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¹ More information:

[http://www.vsnu.nl/files/documenten/Domeinen/Onderzoek/The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice 2012.pdf](http://www.vsnu.nl/files/documenten/Domeinen/Onderzoek/The_Netherlands_Code_of_Conduct_for_Scientific_Practice_2012.pdf)

² It is possible to indicate non-referees (maximum of three names) in ISAAC or, if applicable, directly to ZonMw). The non-referees will NOT be asked to assess your application. Do not incorporate the names in the application. Please submit the names of non-referees via the electronic system ISAAC or Projectnet at the same time as your proposal.

Please submit this application form to NWO in PDF format, using the ISAAC system, which can be accessed at isaac.nwo.nl, or for applications to STW: www.isaac.stw.nl.

NB: Applications to the Medical Sciences unit (ZonMw) should instead use a similar system called ProjectNet, which can be accessed through the website: www.zonmw.nl. For any technical questions regarding submission, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk (isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl).

For any technical questions regarding submission, please contact the ProjectNet helpdesk (projectnet@zonmw.nl).